

JAVASCRIPTDA OB'EKTLARNI YARATISH VA ULARGA MUROJAT QILISH TALIM JARAYONIGA TADBIQI

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JavaScriptda obyektlar barcha ma'lumotlarni bir joyda saqlashga imkon beradi. Obyektlar xususiyatlar va funksiyalardan iborat bo'lishi mumkin.

Obyekt yaratish uchun "object" kalit so'zidan foydalanamiz. Masalan:

```
var car = { model: "BMW",  
year: 2020,  
price: 50000,  
type:function() {  
return "sport";  
}  
};
```

Bu kodda, "car" nomli obyekt yaratdik, unda "model", "year", "price" xususiyatlari va "type" funksiyasi mavjud.

Obyektning xususiyatlariga murojaat uchun nuqta operatoridan foydalanamiz. Masalan:

```
console.log(car.model); // BMW  
console.log(car.year); // 2020
```

Obyektning funksiyalariga murojaat uchun funksiya nomini qavs ichida ishlatamiz. Masalan:

```
console.log(car.type()); // sport
```

JavaScript ta'lim jarayonida turli xil usullarda ishlatilishi mumkin. Masalan, u savollar, o'yinlar va simulatsiyalar kabi interaktiv o'quv materiallarni yaratish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. JavaScript ta'lim boshqaruv tizimlarining funksional sohasini kengaytirish uchun ham ishlatilishi mumkin, bu o'quvchilarga shaxsiy va qiziqarli o'rganish tajribasini beradi.

Obyektlardan tadqiqiy jarayonlarda foydalanish, ma'lumotlarni tashkil qilishda yordam beradi. Masalan, o'quvchi obyektini ism, yosh va baholari kabi xususiyatlari bilan yaratish, o'quvchilar haqida ma'lumotlarni tuzishni yanada murakkablashtiradi. Qo'shimcha ravishda, obyektlar ichidagi funksiyalar ma'lumotlarni oson hisoblash yoki o'zgartirish imkonini beradi. JavaScript o'quvchilarga dasturlash konseptlarini va kodlash ko'nikmalarini o'rganish uchun ham ishlatilishi mumkin, chunki u keng tarqalgan va kirishga qulay dasturlash tillaridan biridir. Barcha holatda, JavaScript ta'lim va o'rganish uchun innovatsion va samarali vositalar taqdim etish orqali joriy ta'limda qadrli o'rin tutishi mumkin.

Bundan tashqari JavaScript dasturlash tili matn asosida ishlaydi va istemolchi va server tomonidan foydalanish mumkin. U veb sahifalarda multimedia-ni boshqaradi va ularni interaktiv qiladi. JavaScript dasturchiga rasmga animatsiya qo'shish yoki sahifadagi kontentni avtomatik ravishda yangilash kabi ko'plab narsalarni amalga oshirishga imkon beradi.

JavaScript sizga tashrif buyuradigan ko'pgina veb-sahifalar bilan muloqot qilish imkonini beradi. Shunchaki, shakllarni to'ldirish, xaritalardan o'tish yoki tadbirga ro'yxatdan o'tish kabi ishlarni bajarganingizning ko'p xil holatlari uchun JavaScript dasturlash tilining ishlatilishi aniq. Misol uchun, JavaScript-dan foydalanilgan savdo savatchiligiga ega bo'lgan veb-sahifada

taxminiy narxni ko'rishni xohlasangiz, siz kiritgan kredit karta ma'lumotlari to'g'ri yoki noto'g'ri ekanligini aniqlash uchun JavaScript ishlatiladi va u ma'lumotlarni bankga o'tkazish uchun internet orqali jo'natiladi.

JavaScript nima uchun ishlatiladi?

JavaScript dunyodagi eng ko'p ishlatiladigan dasturlash tillari orasida joy oladi. U yo'qolgan holda, biz rasmlarni va matnlarni ko'rsatuvchi hech narsani ko'rmaymiz. HTML veb-sahifaning tuzilishi, CSS esa ushbu sahifaga stil qo'shadi, lekin JavaScript dasturlash tilining hayoti beradi.

Bu ajoyib tilda bo'lmaganda, bizneslar qo'shimcha yordam olishadi. Kompaniyalar bugungi onlayn dunyoda mijozlar bilan muloqot o'rnatish uchun JavaScript tiliga qarashadi. JavaScript ning ommaviy ishlatiladigan turlari quyidagilardir:

Interaktiv veb-sahifalarni yaratish

Yuqoridagi haqida muzokiraga chiqqan holda, JavaScript sizning sahifada o'zgarishlarga olib keladigan har qanday ta'sirga javob beruvchi har qanday veb-sayt bilan muloqotni boshlash uchun javob beradi. U yo'qolgan holda, internet juda cheklangan bo'ladi. JavaScript-dan foydalaniladigan oddiy amallar quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- * Savatchaga mahsulot qo'shish va onlayn savdo qilish
- * Muis tugmasini bosish orqali kontent bloklarini kengaytirish yoki yopish
- * Saytda video yoki audio fayllarini ijro etish
- * Animatsiyalarni ko'rsatish
- * Pastga ko'chirilgan menyularni ishlatish

Old end dasturlash

Veb-saytlar foydalanuvchilariga ajoyib ilovalar yaratishga yordam beradigan ko'plab mashhur old-end JavaScript freymvorklari mavjud. Bu freymvorklar Angular, React va Vue kabi ilovalarni o'z ichiga oladi. JavaScript-dan foydalanilgan mashhur ilovalar Netflix, PayPal, YouTube va Facebook.

Orqa uchun dasturlash

JavaScript o'zini HTML va CSS-ga qo'llab-quvvatlashi sifatida nom qilgan holda, u orqa uchun dasturlash tili sifatida ham ajoyib xususiyatlarga ega. Node.js kabi freymvorklar JavaScript tilini server tomonidan kod yaratish uchun ishlatishga imkon beradi.

O'yinlar

JavaScript dasturlash tili oddiy veb-saytlarga yordam berishdan ko'ra, brauzerdagi ko'plab o'yinlarga ham javob beradi. Agar siz dasturlashda boshlanganingiz vaqtni o'tkazish yoki mahoratni oshirish uchun ajoyib.

Sun'iy intellekt

JavaScript-dan foydalanishning relative yangi yonalishi Sun'iy intellekt (AI) da. TensorFlow kabi JavaScript kutubxonalarini dasturchilarga JavaScript-dan foydalanishni taqdim etdi, oldingi ma'lumotlar kategoriyasiga asoslangan kelajakdagi hodisalarni bashorat qiluvchi modellarni yaratish uchun.

JavaScript ning ko'p va turli ishlari dunyoda talab qilinadigan ko'dlash imkonini beradi. Masalan, Inglizdagi Indeed-da oddiy qidiruvda yozilgan vaqtida 13,500 bo'sh ish o'rinlari ko'rsatilgan, shuning uchun, agar siz veb-dasturlash sohasida kasbga kirishni xohlaysiz, uni o'rganish uchun foydali bo'ladi

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